

Surface modification of waste glass powder by plasma treatment: impact on cement paste microstructure and strength development

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Abstract

This study examines the effects of plasma surface treatments on the properties of waste glass powder incorporated into cement-based materials, focusing on its influence on the interfacial transition zones and mechanical performance. Surface modifications were carried out using oxygen and hydrogen plasma treatments to enhance the reactivity of the waste glass powder. Cement composites with 10% and 20% replacement of cement with oxygen plasma-treated waste glass powder showed compressive strengths of 97.7 MPa and 90 MPa, respectively, after 90 days. This represents an increase of 10% to 15% compared to the reference samples without treatment. These enhancements are attributed to the creation of hydrophilic surface properties, which promote better hydration reactions and pozzolanic activity. The oxygen plasma treatment also led to a reduction in fine pore volume and enhanced densification of the interfacial transition zones, contributing to improved durability and material performance. In contrast, hydrogen plasma-treated samples exhibited limited improvements due to the hydrophobic nature of the treated surfaces. These results highlight the potential of oxygen plasma treatment as a sustainable method to optimize the utilization of recycled glass in cement-based materials, achieving significant mechanical and microstructural enhancements.

Keywords: Plasma surface treatment, Waste glass powder, Cementitious materials, Interfacial transition zones, Cement paste

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1. Introduction

With rising environmental concerns and stricter regulations, the construction industry is increasingly focused on sustainable practices, particularly in waste management and resource conservation. The incorporation of waste materials, specifically glass, into concrete production represents a significant advancement in this direction. Traditionally, waste glass – a non-biodegradable material – poses environmental challenges when disposed of in landfills, resulting due to its slow decomposition rate [1]. In 2022, the Czech Republic generated approximately 160,000 tons of waste glass, primarily from packaging, with 75% being recycled and the remaining portion ending up in landfills [2]. Globally, over 36 million tons of waste glass are generated annually, with projections rising to over 50 million tons by 2030 [3]. Furthermore, the increasing decommissioning of photovoltaic panels is expected to contribute significantly to this figure, as glass constitutes around 70% of weight of a solar panel. By 2030, waste glass from photovoltaic panels could add millions of tons globally, compounding the challenges of sustainable waste management [4].

However, with advancements in material science and increasing attention to sustainable construction, research is turning toward using waste glass as a partial replacement for cement and aggregates in concrete. This approach not only reduces landfill burden but also provides an avenue for reducing the carbon footprint of concrete production, as Portland cement manufacturing contributes approximately 5–7% of global CO₂ emissions [5, 6].

Studies indicate that waste glass, when finely ground, exhibits pozzolanic properties, which can enhance both the mechanical and durability characteristics of concrete by forming additional cementitious compounds [7]. This pozzolanic reaction contributes to a denser microstructure, reducing water absorption and increasing durability, particularly important for concrete exposed to harsh conditions, such as coastal environments where chloride resistance is essential [8]. Research shows compressive and flexural strength improvements when glass powder replaces cement in optimized proportions by weight, typically between 10–20%, without compromising structural performance [9, 10].

However, the mechanical properties of concrete containing waste glass vary significantly with sample age. Early-age concrete may exhibit lower initial compressive strength due to the delayed

29 pozzolanic reaction of glass particles, as this reaction requires time to consume calcium hydrox-
30 ide and form stable calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) compounds, which are crucial for strength
31 development [11]. Additionally, the strength is significantly influenced by the quality of the Inter-
32 facial Transition Zone (ITZ), as this zone often represents the weakest link in the microstructure,
33 affecting the transfer of stress between the cement matrix and the glass particles [12]. As a result,
34 concrete containing glass powder often shows a notable increase in strength at later stages, often
35 surpassing control samples after extended curing periods of 90 days or more [13]. Some studies
36 even indicate compressive strength increases continuing up to one year, with gains of 27% or more
37 over control samples in high glass powder mixes [7].

38 To overcome the challenge of slower strength gains at early stages and reduce ITZ, plasma
39 treatments on the surface of fine glass particles have emerged as a promising solution. Plasma sur-
40 face treatments modify the glass surface at a molecular level, increasing its reactivity and promot-
41 ing faster bonding with cementitious compounds during early hydration stages. This enhancement
42 leads to significant improvements in early compressive strength, making plasma-treated glass par-
43 ticles particularly suitable for applications where early load-bearing capacity is essential [14, 15].
44 Plasma treatments thus provide a novel approach to leveraging waste glass in concrete by reducing
45 the need for prolonged curing and enabling faster strength development.

46 For instance, the use of plasma treatment of concrete components may reduce the setting time
47 or increase the strength of tested samples [16, 17]. Indeed, plasma treatment is one of the most
48 versatile and universal methods of material processing. Plasma (as ionised state of matter) can be
49 generated by different methods while final applications are varying based on plasma parameters.
50 For instance, depending on the charged particles energy ("temperature") determined the thermal
51 (with fully or mostly ionised gas) and non-thermal (with weakly or partially ionised gas) plasma,
52 and depending on operated gas pressure, the atmospheric and low-pressure plasma can be distin-
53 guished [18, 19]. Taking into account the variety of gases and mixtures that can be used for plasma
54 generation the possible plasma-material complex physical and chemical interaction processes (and
55 application) includes etching, sputtering, thermal or radiation damage, decomposition, ion implan-
56 tation, surface chemistry modification, deposition and re-deposition of material, etc. [18, 19].

57 Regarding sustainable engineering and environmental applications, the high-temperature plasma
58 is proposed for thermal decomposition of waste (e.g. organic or plastic) as well as metal recycling.
59 Conversely, low-temperature plasma applications include decomposition of greenhouse gases and
60 cleaning of surfaces contaminated with organic substances [19–22]. The plasma treatment of con-
61 crete waste and waste fiberglass has shown promising results in cement-based materials, aligning
62 with sustainable construction requirements for recycled material utilization [23, 24]. The plasma
63 treatment effectively modifies both surface or subsurface properties of glass, influencing its inter-
64 action with water and adhesive properties [25–29]. Due to the fact that for small size materials the
65 surface properties are crucial, the plasma treatment of waste glass particles can significantly affect
66 alkali diffusion and bonding properties. This modification potentially improves both the pozzolanic
67 reaction of glass particles and the overall performance of cement-based composites [23, 25, 29].

68 Plasma surface modifications have established widespread applications across various indus-
69 trial sectors, including automotive manufacturing, medical devices, food packaging, sportswear,
70 agriculture, and electronics [30], yet their implementation in construction materials remains com-
71 paratively limited. Recent advancements in plasma technology, however, demonstrate significant
72 potential for construction applications through high-throughput treatment capabilities and expand-
73 ing industrial-scale processing systems. The efficacy of plasma treatment in construction materials
74 is evidenced by multiple improvements: enhanced physical and mechanical properties of con-
75 struction mortars, resulting in increased strength and reduced setting time [31]; improved frost
76 resistance, water permeability, and chemical resistance in concrete and wood materials [32]; and
77 enhanced adhesion of cement paste to aggregates, leading to superior interfacial transition zone
78 characteristics and overall concrete properties [33]. Furthermore, optimized plasma protocols can
79 offer more cost-effective solutions compared to traditional thermal treatment methods, presenting
80 a viable alternative for surface modification in construction applications [32].

81 The present study seeks to address the challenge of integrating waste glass powder (WGP) into
82 cementitious materials through innovative plasma treatment methods. By focusing on the surface
83 modification of WGP, this research aims to enhance its reactivity and optimize its role as a sup-
84plementary cementitious material. The ultimate goal is to contribute to sustainable construction

85 practices by leveraging WGP's potential to improve mechanical properties, reduce ecological im-
86 pacts, and enable broader recycling applications. The novelty of this study lies in the use of plasma
87 treatment to activate the WGP surface, aiming to enhance pozzolanic reactivity and improve inter-
88 facial bonding within the matrix. This novel approach not only highlights the feasibility of using
89 WGP in advanced cement composites but also establishes a pathway for its practical adoption in
90 the construction industry, paving the way for environmentally responsible material innovations.

91 **2. Materials and samples**

92 The experimental plan of this study is designed to evaluate the impact of WGP on the properties
93 of cement pastes and mortars. The research is divided into two key phases, complemented by sup-
94plementary analyses, to comprehensively understand and quantify the effects of both untreated and
95 plasma-treated WGP. The workflow includes material characterization, experimental preparation,
96 and detailed testing (Tab. 1).

97 Initially, the raw materials were characterized using different techniques such as SEM (mor-
98phology), XRF (chemical composition), XPS (surface analysis), and granulometry (particle size
99 distribution). These analyses established baseline properties for untreated and plasma-treated
100 WGP, providing a foundation for subsequent experiments.

101 In the first phase, the optimal replacement ratio of untreated WGP in cement composites was
102 determined following EN 196-1 standards [34]. Mechanical properties of cement composites such
103 as compressive and flexural strength were assessed at 7, 28, and 90 days to evaluate performance
104 variations at different curing times.

105 The second phase focused on the effects of plasma-treated WGP, specifically oxygen and hy-
106drogen plasma treatments. Cement composites were prepared with treated WGP and tested for
107 strength development, porosity, and microstructural improvements at 28 and 90 days. To support
108 the primary experiments, supplementary analyses included porosimetry for pore size distribution,
109 nanoindentation for quantifying Young's modulus, and XRD for identifying crystalline and amor-
110 phous phases. These analyses were performed on 90-day-old samples to provide deeper insights
111 into the durability and microstructural attributes of the composites, focusing on the treated samples
112 to ensure precise evaluation of plasma effects.

Table 1: Experimental plan summarizing phases, techniques, objectives, and testing frequency.

Phase	Analysis/Technique	Objective	Frequency
Characterization	SEM, XRF, XPS, Granulometry	Baseline properties of WGP	Initial
Phase 1	Mechanical testing (compressive, flexural strength)	Determine optimal WGP replacement ratio	7, 28, 90 days
Phase 2	Plasma treatment evaluation	Assess strength and ITZ improvements	28, 90 days
Supplementary	Porosimetry, Nanoindentation, XRD	Microstructural and durability analysis	90 days

113 This structured approach ensures a comprehensive evaluation of WGP's impact on cementitious
 114 materials, paving the way for sustainable and high-performance construction practices.

115 *2.1. First phase of experiment accord to EN 196-1*

116 In the initial phase of the research, specimens were created according to EN 196-1 with dimen-
 117 sions of 40×40×160 mm. The samples were composed of CEM I 42.5R Portland cement from
 118 Radotín (Czech Republic) [35], which contains a large amount of clinker minerals (more than 95
 119 wt.%). Another component was ground recycled WGP from the packaging industry. This is glass
 120 that cannot be further used in the production of new glass, primarily originating from colored pack-
 121 aging glass sorted into containers in the Czech Republic. The samples were provided by Recifa
 122 JSC, Příbram, CZ, a company that collects and subsequently recycles this material, making it a
 123 real-world material with an annual production of 160 tons/year in the Czech Republic.

124 According to EN 196-1, cement pastes (p) were created, composed only of CEM I 42.5R and
 125 WGP, and cement mortar (m) additionally containing norm silica sand fraction 0/2 mm. WGP was
 126 consistently used as a substitute for cement at levels of 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% by
 127 weight (wt.%). The water coefficient, i.e., the ratio of water to binder (w/b), was equal to 0.35 for
 128 the cement paste samples and 0.5 for the mortar samples. The amount of water substitution was
 129 always the same for each paste and mortar samples so that the results could be compared with each

130 other. The composition of the individual tested mixtures in the first phase of the experiment can be
 131 seen in Tab. 2.

132 The specimens were cast into molds and kept at a laboratory temperature of 25 ± 1 °C and a
 133 relative humidity of $50\pm 5\%$ until demolding after 24 hours. Subsequently, they were placed in a
 134 water bath at 25 ± 1 °C and stored until testing. Testing was performed at intervals of 7, 28, and 90
 135 days, using 5 specimens for each interval.

Table 2: Material proportions and flow test results for different mixes.

Designation	CEM I 42.5R	WGP	Silica sand	Water	w/c	Flow test spill
	[kg]	[kg]	[kg]	[kg]	[-]	[mm]
REFp	3.00	0.00	0.00	1.05	0.35	205±5
G10p	2.70	0.30	0.00	1.05	0.39	210±5
G20p	2.40	0.60	0.00	1.05	0.44	205±9
G30p	2.10	0.90	0.00	1.05	0.50	215±9
G40p	1.80	1.20	0.00	1.05	0.58	205±1
G50p	1.50	1.50	0.00	1.05	0.70	195±5
REFm	0.90	0.00	2.70	0.45	0.50	171±5
G10m	0.81	0.09	2.70	0.45	0.56	168±5
G20m	0.72	0.18	2.70	0.45	0.63	175±5
G30m	0.63	0.27	2.70	0.45	0.71	181±5
G40m	0.54	0.36	2.70	0.45	0.83	170±5
G50m	0.45	0.45	2.70	0.45	1.00	167±5

136 2.2. Second phase of experiment

137 In the second phase of the experiment, samples containing untreated and plasma-treated WGP
 138 and CEM I 42.5R Portland cement paste were created. The specimens had standard dimensions of
 139 $20\times 20\times 100$ mm, and a total of 6 specimens were prepared for each set: 3 specimens were tested
 140 after 28 days, and 3 specimens after 90 days. The specimens were demolded after 24 hours and
 141 stored at laboratory temperature 25 ± 1 °C in a water bath until the designated testing age. The

142 WGP was exposed to radiofrequency (r.f.) plasma treatment in the large area low pressure system
 143 (AK 400, Roth&Rau) [36]. For the treatment process the WGP was placed in glassy Petri dishes
 144 in the amount of a few grams just to cover the dish bottom. The plasma exposure procedure was
 145 performed for 5 minutes in an oxygen (flow 100 sccm) or hydrogen (flow 200 sccm) at pressure
 146 15 Pa and temperature below 50 °C, marked as room temperature. The r.f. plasma discharge
 147 was ignited at power 600 W and average negative bias voltage -15 V applied to the substrate
 148 holder with size 20×30 cm. In each treatment process, the procedure of r.f. plasma exposure
 149 was repeated 4 times with WGP mixing. The employed plasma treatment equipment is laboratory
 150 based (i.e. oriented on materials properties research) and not very suitable for the fast processing
 151 of large, powder-like material quantities. The amount of plasma treated WGP required for cement
 152 pastes testing was prepared within a few weeks (two plasma types). After processing the plasma
 153 treated WGP was stored in containers whilst its interaction with the atmosphere or aging were
 154 not considered. Due to the time limitation of the plasma treatments for WGP amount processing,
 155 samples were created with 10 and 20 wt.% cement replacement using differently treated WGP. The
 156 water w/b coefficient was set to 0.35 for all samples. The resulting composition of samples of the
 157 second phase of experiment can be seen in Tab. 3.

Table 3: Composition of cement pastes with untreated and plasma-treated WGP for the second phase of the experiment.

Designation	CEM I 42.5R [g]	WGP [g]	Water [g]	w/c [-]	Type of plasma treatment
REF	300	0	105	0.35	No treatment
G10_REF	270	30	105	0.39	No treatment
G20_REF	240	60	105	0.44	No treatment
G10_O	270	30	105	0.39	Oxygen plasma
G20_O	240	60	105	0.44	Oxygen plasma
G10_H	270	30	105	0.39	Hydrogen plasma
G20_H	240	60	105	0.44	Hydrogen plasma

158 Additionally, polished cross-sections were prepared from these samples for scanning electron
 159 microscopy (SEM) and nanoindentation analysis. The polished sections were created from frag-
 160 ments of the specimens obtained during destructive testing. Specifically, a 50 mm slice was cut

161 from the center of the sample after three-point bending test. These fragments were vacuum-
162 impregnated with epoxy resin (Struers EpoFix Kit) and subsequently ground and polished in
163 several steps. Grinding was performed using SiC foils with grit sizes of 500, 1200, 2000, and
164 4000 grain/inch², followed by polishing with a cloth and diamond suspensions with particle sizes
165 of 3 and 1 microns [37]. The resulting surface achieved sufficient flatness and quality for sub-
166 sequent analytical techniques. For SEM analysis, the surface of the samples was sputter-coated
167 with a thin platinum layer of 3 nm to enhance conductivity and prevent charging during electron
168 microscopy.

169 **3. Experimental methods**

170 *3.1. Characterization of raw materials*

171 Characterization of the input raw materials (i.e. before cement composites preparation) was
172 carried out to determine the size, shape, and chemical composition of each fine material. The shape
173 and character of the particles were determined using a Phenom XL SEM (ThermoFisher Scientific).
174 For this purpose, structure mapping using Backscattered Electron (BSE) at 1k \times magnification and
175 an 8 \times 8 image matrix was employed, which was then analyzed using ImageJ software to determine
176 the circularity, roundness, and aspect ratio of the grains. The measurement process using ImageJ
177 software is shown in Fig. 1. The process involves segmenting particles from the background and
178 analyzing their shapes by fitting ellipses to determine their major (MA) and minor (MI) axes.

179 Furthermore, XRF analysis was performed to describe the chemical composition of the dif-
180 ferent materials and to calculate the abundance of each clinker mineral in the cement according
181 to the Bogue equation [38, 39]. The XRF analysis was performed on a Spectro Xepos equipped
182 with a 50 W/60 kV X-ray tube. Laser granulometry was performed using a Fritsch Analysette
183 22 MicroTec Plus to describe the grain size. The device was equipped with a red and green laser
184 source (wavelengths 532 and 940 nm) and was able to detect particles ranging in size from 0.08 to
185 1800 μ m in diameter. The particles were dispersed in an ultrasonic bath. The Fraunhofer diffrac-
186 tion model was used to evaluate the diffraction patterns.

187 The surface elemental composition of WGP was analysed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
188 (XPS). For this, untreated and plasma-treated WGP were spread in the uniform layers on a Cu

Figure 1: Procedure for determining shape characteristics of grains using image analysis: (a) Overview of the particle distribution, (b) Selected region of interest, (c) Binary segmentation of particles, and (d) Shape analysis with fitted ellipses and parameter labeling.

189 tape. The XPS spectra were acquired using AxisSUPRA photoelectron spectrometer (Kratos Ana-
190 lytical) with a base pressure of 10^{-7} Pa. Monochromatized Al $K\alpha$ X-ray source, hybrid lens mode
191 and charge compensation were used for all measurements. The data for atomic concentration of
192 elements estimating were acquired using a resolution of 80. Additionally, resolution 10 was used
193 for acquiring Si 2p, C 1s and O 1s regions for detailed analyses. Due to employed charge com-
194 pensation the XPS spectra were shifted (about 3–4 eV) to lower binding energies compared to
195 previously published data [40]. Therefore, for spectra correction, the Si 2p_{3/2} peak was fixed at
196 103.7 eV. Additionally, to calibrate intensities of spectra, all spectra were normalised to intensities
197 of Si 2p doublets.

198 Atomic concentrations of elements were calculated using ESCApe software provided by Kratos
199 Analytical (relative sensitivity factors built in the software and transmission function determined
200 for measurement settings were used). Spectral components fitting was performed in the KolXPD
201 software by peaks or doublets of Voigt profile. The Shirley background was subtracted from all
202 spectra while the ratio between Lorentzian and Gaussian parts of peaks were left free (0.3 at max-
203 imum).

204 The interaction of WGP with deionized (DI) water was studied via zeta (ζ) potential and
205 pH (potential of hydrogen) measurements using Zetasizer Nano ZS – ZEN3600 equipped with
206 multi-purpose titrator MPT-2 (Malvern Panalytical). The zeta potentials of highly diluted WGP
207 suspensions were determined using Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS) mode applicable for
208 particles with sizes from 3.8 nm to 100 nm.

209 *3.2. Testing of stiffness and strength*

210 The dynamic Young's modulus was determined from the natural frequencies of $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm
211 samples using Brüel & Kjaer type 3560-B-120 [41]. For the $20 \times 20 \times 100$ mm samples, the natural
212 frequencies could not be determined due to their size. The specimens were further subjected to
213 destructive testing after 7, 28 and 90 days of hardening in the case of the $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm spec-
214 imens and after 28 and 90 days in the case of the $20 \times 20 \times 100$ mm specimens. First, the flexural
215 strength was determined in a three-point displacement-controlled test setup at a constant speed of
216 0.1 mm/s. The spacing between the supports was 100 mm for the $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm specimens and

217 80 mm for the 20×20×100 mm specimens, and each mixture was represented by six specimens.
218 Furthermore, the fractured halves of the specimens, after the three-point bending test were loaded
219 over the effective area of 40×40 mm and 20×20 mm, respectively in uniaxial compression at a
220 crosshead displacement rate of 0.3 mm/s to determine the compressive strength.

221 3.3. Porosimetry

222 The pore size distribution of the samples was studied using mercury intrusion porosimetry
223 (MIP), which provides detailed information about the pore size and volume within the material.
224 The measurements were performed using Pascal 140 and Pascal 440 porosimeters (ThermoFisher
225 Scientific), capable of analyzing pore sizes ranging from 3 nm to 100 μm. Prior to the analysis, the
226 samples were carefully dried at a temperature of 60 °C for 24 hours to remove any residual moisture
227 that could affect the results, ensuring accurate pore volume and size measurements. The average
228 dry sample weight used for the measurements was approximately 1 gram, which is sufficient to
229 achieve representative results. The Pascal 140 porosimeter was used for low-pressure intrusion to
230 assess larger pores, while the Pascal 440 was employed for high-pressure measurements, enabling
231 the detection of smaller pores.

232 3.3.1. Microscopy

233 Microscopic phase analysis was performed using a FEG SEM Merlin (ZEISS Microscopy)
234 equipped with a Schottky cathode. The morphology was mapped using BSE with a resolution
235 of 50-100 nm. Microanalysis of chemical composition was performed using an X-ray energy
236 dispersive spectrometer – EDS (Oxford Instruments). The SEM setup was as follows: accelerating
237 voltage 15 kV, current 2 nA, working table distance 8.5 mm, single point measurement time 60 μs
238 and resolution 1024 px. The BSE results indicated the individual phases were distributed along
239 a space, resulting in different grayscale densities and images of these phases, obtained at 500×
240 and 1k× magnification. Next, the composition of each phase was studied by EDS, both by spot
241 to determine the weight and atomic percentage of each element, and by line scans to reveal the
242 composition of the transition zones around the grains of the WGP. These transition zones were
243 studied on five carefully selected grains of 25-40 μm diameter; three line scans were placed over
244 each grain. The phases were identified from the elemental compositions using stoichiometry.

245 3.3.2. X-ray diffraction

246 Powder diffraction data from the cement composite samples were collected using the Bragg-
247 Brentano focusing configuration on the powder diffractometer Empyrean of PANalytical ($\lambda_{\text{Cu},\text{K}\alpha}$
248 = 1.54184 Å) that was equipped with a fixed divergent slit and PIXcel3D detector with 255 stripes.
249 The measurement was made in 1D continuous mode from 5 to 100 ° 2θ with 0.013 ° step size and
250 for 150 s per step. Each scan was repeated nine times. HighscorePlus software and Rietveld fitting
251 method was used for mineralogical phase analysis and materials identification.

252 3.4. Nanoindentation

253 Grid nanoindentation measurements were performed using the Hysitron TI-980 TriboInden-
254 ter equipped with a Berkovich tip calibrated on a fused quartz standard ($E_r=69.61\pm 1.14$ GPa,
255 $H=9.16\pm 0.32$ GPa). The samples (REF, G20_REF, G20_O, G20_H) were tested in a load-controlled
256 regime with accelerated mapping mode (XPM), employing a trapezoidal loading diagram consist-
257 ing of linear loading for 0.1 s up to a maximum force of 1.5 mN, holding the maximum force
258 for 0.1 s, and unloading for 0.1 s. The combination of maximum force and indent separation was
259 selected to avoid indent interactions [42]. Five grids of 22×22 indents, with a spacing of 2.5 μm
260 between indents, covering an area of 52.5×52.5 μm², were performed on each sample. Totally
261 2420 indents were performed on each sample. For the G20_REF, G20_O, and G20_H samples, the
262 grid's location was specifically positioned at the interface of the glass particle and cement matrix
263 to cover approximately the distance in the ITZ (30–40 μm). The lateral move speed of the indenter
264 was set to 10 μm/s with a serpentine piezo translation protocol to ensure the smallest total time
265 (273 s) for measuring one grid and to avoid errors from thermal drift [43].

266 Young's modulus, E , was determined from measurements using the Oliver and Pharr the-
267 ory [44], which is based on Sneddon's analytical solution for an indenter pressed into an elas-
268 tic half-space [45]. The reduced modulus E_r was calculated from the analysis of the unloading
269 segment of the load-displacement curve:

$$E_r = \frac{S\sqrt{\pi}}{2\beta\sqrt{A_c}}, \quad (1)$$

270 where A_c represents the tip projected contact area, S describes the elastic unloading stiffness,
271 and β is the tip geometry correction factor ($\beta = 1.034$ for Berkovich tip [46]). The reduced

272 modulus characterizes the combined elastic stiffness of the material and the nanoindentation tip.
273 Subsequently, the Young's modulus of the isotropic material was calculated using the equation:

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{1 - \nu^2}{E} + \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i}, \quad (2)$$

274 where E_i and ν_i are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the nanoindentation tip, respec-
275 tively (for diamond tip $E_i = 1141$ GPa and $\nu_i = 0.07$). The Poisson's ratio of a sample, ν , was
276 assumed to be 0.2 in all cases [47, 48].

277 4. Results and discussion

278 4.1. Characterization of raw materials

279 4.1.1. Granulometry and structural analysis

280 The SEM images in Fig. 2 (a-c) provide a visual comparison of untreated (WGP ref.) and
281 plasma-treated (WGP O₂, WGP H₂) glass particles. At the given magnification (4.5k×), no signif-
282 icant surface changes are visible between untreated (a), oxygen-treated (b), and hydrogen-treated
283 (c) glass particles. This suggests that plasma treatments may not produce observable morpho-
284 logical changes at the microscale. Any modifications introduced by the plasma treatments might
285 only be apparent at higher, nanoscale magnifications, where finer surface features could poten-
286 tially reveal differences. This supports the findings by Matos and Sousa-Coutinho, who noted that
287 certain treatments may only produce structural effects at the nanoscale. For the purposes of this
288 study, WGP was used, with image SEM analysis of its shape and size characteristics of individual
289 grains [49]. Tab. 4 presents the main shape parameters, specifically circularity, roundness, and as-
290 pect ratio. The analysis showed that the differences in circularity and aspect ratio values between
291 the reference glass and the samples treated with oxygen and hydrogen plasma are within the range
292 of the standard deviation. This indicates that plasma treatments do not have a statistically signifi-
293 cant effect on the shape of the WGP grains, and thus do not lead to substantial changes in particle
294 morphology as a result of these treatments.

295 The grain size curve of the materials used can be seen in Fig. 3. The particle size distribution
296 graph shows that, although both raw materials (cement and WGP) contain particles of a similar

Figure 2: Images from the SEM microscope, magnified $4.5k\times$, BSE detector: a) untreated WGP, b) WGP treated with oxygen plasma O_2 , c) WGP treated with hydrogen plasma H_2 .

Table 4: Shape characteristics of individual grains of WGP with standard deviations.

Designation	Number of grains tested [pc]	Circularity [-]	Roundness [-]	Aspect Ratio [-]
WGP ref.	8122	0.38 ± 0.19	0.57 ± 0.17	1.96 ± 0.73
WGP O_2	8738	0.30 ± 0.17	0.57 ± 0.17	1.95 ± 0.71
WGP H_2	6457	0.30 ± 0.18	0.57 ± 0.17	1.92 ± 0.66

297 fraction, WGP exhibits a coarser distribution, which may impact its behavior in the cement matrix.
 298 Due to its particle size, WGP has the potential to contribute to long-term strength development
 299 through secondary pozzolanic reactions. This behavior is consistent with the findings of Zhu et
 300 al., who observed similar effects for WGP when used as a supplementary material, leading to
 301 strength enhancement at later stages due to the gradual formation of additional C-S-H phases [50].
 302 Additionally, Shaikh and Supit reported analogous behavior for other waste materials exhibiting
 303 pozzolanic reactivity, further supporting this observation [51].

304 4.1.2. Chemical and mineralogical composition

305 The chemical composition of Portland cement (CEM I 42.5R), WGP and normative sand was
 306 analyzed using XRF (Tab. 5). Portland cement is primarily composed of clinker minerals, mak-
 307 ing up approximately $95\%\pm 5\%$ of its total content, with tricalcium silicate (C_3S) being the most
 308 abundant phase (Tab. 6). In addition to high levels of calcium oxide (CaO), essential for hydration
 309 reactions, Portland cement contains notable amounts of silicon dioxide (SiO_2) and other oxides.

Figure 3: Particle size distribution of waste glass powder (WGP), Portland cement (CEM I 42.5R), and normative sand. The cumulative volume (%) is represented by solid lines, while the volume (%) is represented by dashed lines.

Table 5: Chemical composition of Portland cement, WGP and Normative sand (XRF results).

Chemical composition [%]	CEM I 42.5R	WGP	Normative sand
CaO	64.8	2.62	-
SiO ₂	20.1	81.20	99.1
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.51	-	0.11
Na ₂ O	-	14.40	-
MgO	1.92	-	-
Al ₂ O ₃	4.02	-	0.23
SO ₃	3.01	-	-
Other elements	0.45	0.14	0.11
LOI	3.05	2.01	0.45

Table 6: Mineralogical composition of CEM I 42.5R calculated by using the Bogue method [38, 39].

Mineralogical composition [%]	CEM I 42.5R
C ₃ S	74.6
C ₂ S	7.2
C ₃ A	8.1
C ₄ AF	8.5
MgO	1.6

310 In contrast, WGP is mainly composed of silicon dioxide (SiO₂) and has a relatively high
 311 sodium oxide (Na₂O) content (14.4%), with much lower calcium oxide (CaO). The high SiO₂
 312 content in WGP supports its potential as a pozzolanic material. Studie by Zhao et al. have high-
 313 lighted that SiO₂ from waste glass can react with calcium hydroxide in cement paste, forming
 314 additional calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel, which enhances long-term durability and struc-
 315 tural integrity [52]. Similarly, Mallum et al. confirmed that the SiO₂-rich composition of WGP
 316 contributes to the densification of the cement matrix through secondary C-S-H gel formation, re-
 317 inforcing concrete’s durability and mechanical performance [53].

318 However, the Na₂O content in WGP poses a risk of alkali-silica reaction (ASR) when mixed
 319 with reactive aggregates. Bignozzi et al. noted that Na₂O levels above approximately 12% can
 320 significantly increase ASR risk, leading to potential expansion and cracking in the concrete if not
 321 managed properly [54]. Therefore, while the high silica content makes WGP a valuable supple-
 322 mentary cementitious material, careful consideration of its alkali content is essential to minimize
 323 ASR risks, as supported by Keerio et al., who emphasized the importance of alkali management in
 324 glass-based cement composites [55].

325 4.1.3. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

326 Chemical elements detected on the WGP surface are summarised in Tab. 7. Signals originating
 327 from oxygen, silicon and carbon dominate the measurements. The observed sodium and calcium
 328 were considered as main network modifiers in the silica network of WGP samples, indicating a
 329 prevalent soda-lime nature of the recycled glass [56–58]. The amount of Mg and Al was estimated

330 to be slightly less than 1% while traces of other elements, such as Fe, N, K, F, Cl, were below 0.5 %,
331 i.e. close to the detection limit of the system. It is highly likely that these elements originate from
332 processing or residual contaminants. These results are corroborate with the bulk WGP composition
333 analyzed by XRF (Tab. 5).

334 The relatively high carbon contamination present in all samples was reported previously for this
335 type of WGP [59] and is attributed to the source of glass waste, i.e. packaging industry, and ground-
336 ing process. It is noteworthy that the lowest amount of carbon, observed for the sample treated in
337 oxygen plasma, correlates with the highest concentration of Na, Mg and Al. Frequently, in the
338 waste glass reuse only the composition of recycled glass itself is considered [56–58] overlooking
339 the issue of recycling contamination or glass interaction with air [29, 60, 61] while particle's sur-
340 face play dominant role at the early hydration stages. Indeed, according to our observations [62]
341 the detected carbon is present as ultra-thin traces on the surface of particles which may further af-
342 fect the interface of the glass particle and cement matrix, especially WGP hydrophobic/hydrophilic
343 properties.

344 Further analysis of dominating surface elements (Si, C and O) based on core levels XPS spectra
345 decomposition reveals the following. Most of the Si 2p signal originates from amorphous SiO₂
346 where silicon is present in the 4+ oxidation state with some traces (below 1 %) of Si⁺. Next,
347 Fig. 4 shows C 1s and O 1s XPS spectra deconvoluted to different bonding states. The C 1s
348 region was fitted by four peaks corresponding to carbon bonded to C-C (aliphatic carbon), C-O,
349 C-O(H), C=O, and COOH (from lower binding energies) [63, 64]. Because the real nature and
350 origin of contamination are unknown, we consider only the most common carbon-oxygen bonding
351 states for simplification. The O 1s region was fitted by six peaks at 534.6, 533.4, 533.0, 531.8,
352 531.7, and 530.4 eV while the structure at around 538 eV originates from Na KLL auger electrons.
353 From higher to lower binding energy, these peaks correspond to hydrous species bound to silicon
354 (Si-OH/H₂O), bridging oxygen (Si-O-Si), C-O(H), COOH (or HO-C=O) overlapped with non-
355 bridging oxygen Si-O-M (where M is a network modifier), and C=O [65, 66]. Because the peaks
356 are partially overlapping, the intensities of the O 1s carbon-oxygen peaks (C-O(H), COOH and
357 C=O) were fixed to contribute equally as the corresponding C 1s carbon-oxygen peaks.

Figure 4: Deconvolution of O 1s and C 1s XPS spectra.

358 As it is seen from Tab. 7 and Fig. 4, the surface carbon contamination is present in all samples.
 359 Its amount was reduced by approx. 30 % after O₂ plasma treatment (signal from almost all other
 360 elements became higher) [29], while H₂ plasma treatment affects mainly hydroxyl groups keeping
 361 carbon on the glass particles with its possible transformation to aliphatic carbon and redistribution
 362 (signal from carbon became stronger by 22% while all other decreased) [62]. Although the carbon
 363 removal by oxygen plasma was not complete (or restored due to reabsorption from air), its amount
 364 decreasing may positively affect the interaction of glass particles with water (more hydrophilic
 365 surface) and used binder.

Table 7: Atomic concentration of chemical elements derived from the XPS measurements.

Designation	O [at.%]	Si [at.%]	C [at.%]	Na [at.%]	Ca [at.%]	Mg [at.%]	Al [at.%]
WGP ref.	39.8	17.4	31.6	6.7	2.0	0.8	0.7
WGP O ₂	45.2	20.3	21.8	8.1	1.6	0.9	0.8
WGP H ₂	35.5	16.7	38.5	5.5	1.5	0.7	0.7

366 4.1.4. The pH and surface potential

367 The pH and surface potential (ζ -potential) measurements of untreated and plasma treated WGP
 368 water suspensions are summarised in Tab. 8. It can be seen that dispersing of ground WGP in DI
 369 water led to base suspension with pH of 9.9 ± 0.5 . The origin of this is attributed to the result of
 370 present in WGP sodium and calcium based compounds (oxides) leaching and the large surface of
 371 glass particles interacting with water [60]. The plasma treatment does not significantly change
 372 the pH (the same values within error are observed) since the employed low temperature plasma
 373 treatment conditions should not affect the amount of alkali [25].

Table 8: The pH and surface potential measurements of WGP.

	DI water	WGP ref.	WGP O ₂	WGP H ₂
pH	6.6 ± 0.5	9.9 ± 0.5	10.0 ± 0.5	9.9 ± 0.5
ζ -potential [mV]	-	-31 ± 6	-35 ± 6	-32 ± 6

374 The negative ζ -potential for untreated WGP in DI water with a median value -31 mV was ob-

375 served. The hydrogen plasma treatment led to WGP with a similar negative ζ -potential of -31 mV
376 median value. Finally, WGP after the oxygen plasma treatment demonstrates slightly higher neg-
377 ative ζ -potential with a median value -35 mV. The relatively high negative values of ζ -potentials
378 mean that all analyzed powders can be well dispersed in water.

379 4.2. Mechanical properties of pastes

380 4.2.1. First phase

381 Overall, the substitution of cement with untreated WGP in both pastes and mortars led to a
382 decrease in dynamic Young's modulus (Fig. 5), flexural strength (Fig. 6), and compressive strength
383 (Fig. 7). This trend aligns with findings from other studies, which indicate that replacing reactive
384 cement with less reactive materials, such as WGP, generally results in lower early-age mechanical
385 properties. For example, Shaikh and Supit observed similar reductions in strength when using high-
386 SiO_2 supplementary materials like WGP, attributing the decline to slower pozzolanic reactions
387 compared to the rapid hydration of clinker minerals [51].

388 In terms of long-term performance, the gradual increase in strength over time in WGP-containing
389 samples suggests that the pozzolanic activity of WGP contributes to strength development at later
390 curing stages. This is consistent with observations by Matos and Sousa-Coutinho, who reported
391 that WGP can enhance the microstructure and durability of concrete over time due to its slow-
392 reacting pozzolanic properties [49]. Additionally, Hassani et al. demonstrated that WGP, when
393 finely ground, forms secondary C-S-H gel, which densifies the cement matrix and improves dura-
394 bility in the long term [67].

395 Moreover, the reduction in flexural and compressive strength with higher WGP content (e.g.,
396 40 % G40p, G40m and 50% G50p, G50m) is in line with results from Mallum et al., who showed
397 that high replacement levels often compromise early-age strength due to the limited initial reac-
398 tivity of glass [53]. However, at lower replacement levels, such as 10% (G10p, G10m) and 20%
399 (G20p, G20m), the decline in mechanical properties is less severe. This observation supports the
400 findings of Bignozzi et al., who found that partial replacements below 20% tend to maintain an
401 acceptable balance between sustainability benefits and structural performance [54].

402 Based on these findings and comparisons with existing research, the second phase of the ex-

Figure 5: Development of the dynamic Young's modulus of cement pastes (p) and mortars (m) during the first 90 days of hardening with standard deviations. REF denotes the reference composition without glass. G indicates the replacement of cement with WGP at 10, 20, 30, 40, or 50 wt. % (see Tab. 2 for composition).

Figure 6: Flexural strength of cement pastes (p) and mortars (m) with standard deviations. REF denotes the reference composition without glass, while G indicates the replacement of cement with WGP at 10, 20, 30, 40, or 50 wt. % (see Tab. 2 for composition).

Figure 7: Compressive strength of cement pastes (p) and mortar (m) with standard deviations. REF denotes the reference composition without glass, while G indicates the replacement of cement with WGP at 10, 20, 30, 40, or 50 wt. % (see Tab. 2 for composition).

403 periment focuses specifically on 10% and 20% WGP content. In this phase, plasma treatments is
404 applied to the WGP to investigate whether surface modifications can enhance its reactivity, thereby
405 improving the early-age strength and overall performance of the cement composites.

406 4.2.2. Second phase

407 The graphs illustrate the effects of untreated, oxygen-treated, and hydrogen-treated WGP at
408 10% and 20% replacement levels on flexural (Fig. 8) and compressive strength (Fig. 9) at 28 and
409 90 days. At 10% replacement, samples with oxygen-treated WGP (G10_O) showed a notable in-
410 crease in both flexural and compressive strengths compared to the untreated reference (G10_REF),
411 with an approximate 10% improvement in compressive strength at 90 days. In contrast, hydrogen-
412 treated samples (G10_H and G20_H) displayed strengths similar to or slightly below those of the
413 untreated references, indicating limited benefit from hydrogen treatment.

Figure 8: Flexural strength of cement pastes containing untreated (REF), oxygen-treated (O), and hydrogen-treated (H) WGP with standard deviation. Values are expressed as a percentage relative to the reference sample.

414 While previous studies have discussed the effects of supplementary materials like WGP on
415 strength development in cement composites, none have explored plasma treatment for enhancing

Figure 9: Compressive strength of cement pastes containing untreated (REF), oxygen-treated (O), and hydrogen-treated (H) WGP with standard deviations. Values are expressed as a percentage relative to the reference sample.

416 reactivity and bonding characteristics of WGP within a cementitious matrix. The use of oxygen
 417 plasma treatment is advantageous as it activates the WGP surface, enhancing pozzolanic reactivity
 418 and improving interfacial bonding within the matrix. These findings are consistent with the work of
 419 Hlůžek et al., who investigated the use of plasma treatment to improve bonding between synthetic
 420 fibers and a cementitious matrix using recycled concrete powder [68]. Study also concluded that
 421 oxygen plasma treatment was more effective than hydrogen in enhancing the fiber-matrix interface,
 422 resulting in improved composite performance.

423 4.3. Porosity

424 The pore size distribution graph illustrates the differences in pore volume across untreated
 425 (REF), oxygen-treated, and hydrogen-treated WGP-cement composites (Fig. 10). The untreated
 426 sample (REF) shows a lower overall pore volume, particularly within the 0.01–1 μm range, in-
 427 dicating a denser microstructure. This aligns with findings by Prokopski and Langier, who noted
 428 that a reduction in capillary pores typically enhances compressive strength and durability in cement
 429 composites [69].

430 The oxygen-treated sample (G20_O) demonstrates a reduction in finer pores compared to
 431 hydrogen-treated samples. This suggests that oxygen plasma promotes secondary C-S-H gel for-
 432 mation, filling smaller pores and creating a more compact structure, as observed by Shafiei and
 433 Hillemeier in similar treatments for enhanced durability [33]. The denser pore structure may re-
 434 duce permeability, potentially improving resistance to environmental degradation [70].

435 In contrast, the hydrogen-treated samples (G20_H and G10_H) show higher pore volumes
 436 across most pore sizes, particularly in the critical capillary range. This distribution suggests that
 437 hydrogen treatment may not refine the pore structure as effectively as oxygen, a finding consistent
 438 with Akçaoğlu et al., who reported that a high capillary pore volume can compromise long-term
 439 durability in concrete composites [71].

Figure 10: Pore size distribution of cement pastes with various glass powder treatments. The incremental pore volume (cm^3/g) is represented by solid lines, and the cumulative pore volume (cm^3/g) by dashed lines, plotted against pore diameter (μm).

440 4.4. Microstructural and phase analysis

441 4.4.1. Microstructure

442 SEM and EDS analyses revealed differences in the structure and chemical composition of the
 443 ITZ between untreated, oxygen-treated, and hydrogen-treated samples (Fig. 11). In all cases, the

444 ITZ thickness was approximately 10 μm , but its properties varied depending on the treatment
445 method. In untreated samples, the ITZ was highly porous and contained large portlandite (CH)
446 crystals, which reduce van der Waals forces and consequently the overall mechanical strength [72].
447 The Ca/Si ratio in this zone ranged from 1.5 to 2.0, corresponding to low-density C-S-H (LD C-S-
448 H) gel with lower mechanical properties [73]. In oxygen- and hydrogen-treated samples, the ITZ
449 thickness remained approximately 10 μm , but the chemical composition and microstructure im-
450 proved. SEM imaging and analysis showed a reduction in the Ca/Si ratio to around 1.5, which led
451 to the formation of LD C-S-H gel with improved properties. The presence of amorphous silica from
452 the treated WGP promoted secondary C-S-H gel formation, contributing to notable strength gains
453 at later stages [70, 74]. These microstructural improvements resulted in higher tensile and com-
454 pressive strengths, with oxygen- and hydrogen-treated samples exhibiting comparable mechanical
455 properties and outperforming the untreated samples.

456 Despite these observable improvements, the SEM images (Fig. 12) did not show a fundamental
457 difference in the visual representation of individual phases between oxygen- and hydrogen-treated
458 samples. In both cases, the primary phases — unhydrated clinker, portlandite (CH), and C-S-H gel
459 — appeared similar in grayscale. However, untreated samples exhibited more pronounced porosity
460 and larger portlandite crystals within the ITZ, as previously noted. In contrast, the quantitative
461 EDS analysis revealed a more compact and refined ITZ in the oxygen-treated samples, with a
462 gradual Ca/Si ratio transition. This smoother transition differs from the sharp boundary observed
463 in untreated and hydrogen-treated samples, where the larger portlandite crystals likely disrupted
464 the homogeneity of the ITZ. This subtle microstructural refinement supports the observed increase
465 in flexural and compressive strengths, as oxygen-treated samples consistently outperformed both
466 the untreated and hydrogen-treated ones.

467 4.4.2. Mineralogical composition

468 The XRD diffractograms of analyzed samples from the second phase of experiments are shown
469 in Fig. 13. In all tested samples the clear dominance of the following materials (as indicated
470 by characteristic peaks) was observed: Portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), Calcite (CaCO_3), Belite/Dicalcium
471 silicate (Ca_2SiO_4), Ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{27}$), and Alite/Hatrurite (Ca_3SiO_5) [75–

Figure 11: EDS line scan analysis over a 15 μm distance by SEM, showing the interfacial transition zone (ITZ) between glass grains and the cement matrix in samples with 20% WGP. (a) Untreated WGP (G20_REF), (b) oxygen-treated WGP (G20_O), and (c) hydrogen-treated WGP (G20_H). The graphs display the weight and atomic ratios of silicon (Si), calcium (Ca), and oxygen (O), along with the Ca/Si ratio.

Figure 12: SEM images captured using backscattered electrons at 1000× magnification, showing microstructural differences in cement paste samples. (a) Reference sample without WGP (REF), (b) sample with 20% untreated WGP (G20_REF), (c) sample with 20% oxygen-treated WGP (G20_O), and (d) sample with 20% hydrogen-treated WGP (G20_H). Key microstructural components are labelled: (1) unhydrated clinker, (2) C-S-H gel, (3) portlandite, (4) pores, and (5) WGP.

472 78]. Here it should be noted that sharp, well-defined peaks in XRD patterns can be observed only
 473 for crystalline materials while amorphous phases are generally represented by broad humps in
 474 spectra that are hard to be distinguishable. In the current experiments the most evident hump of
 475 amorphous phases (that should be about 60% of the whole sample) observed in all spectra was
 476 found in region 26-36°.

Figure 13: XRD diffractograms of the analyzed samples.

477 The reference sample (G10_REF) with 10 wt.% WGP contained between 44–46% portlandite
 478 and 11–13% unhydrated clinker. The G10_O sample, containing 10 wt.% WGP treated with oxy-
 479 gen plasma, showed a higher portlandite content in the range of 48–50% and a decrease in un-
 480 hydrated clinker to 9–11%. When recalculated for the total volume of material (including both
 481 amorphous and crystalline phases), no significant changes exceeding the standard deviations were
 482 observed, but a slight trend was evident, showing an increase in crystalline hydration products and
 483 a reduction in unhydrated clinker. These results align with previous findings that approximately
 484 40% crystalline phases are formed when using the same cement and water-to-binder ratio [73], and
 485 that the amount of hydrated products is directly correlated with the final properties of the cement

486 matrix [79]. This outcome suggests improved hydration and supports other conclusions discussed
487 in this article.

488 The presence of calcite can indicate a partial carbonation, which can appear during the sample
489 preparation or analysis [75–78]. Finally, it should be mentioned that in the tested all samples were
490 observed traces (in range with XRD sensitivity) of other materials, among which the Gypsum have
491 the highest amount, yet not exceeding 2%.

492 4.4.3. Nanoindentation

493 A wide range of Young's modulus (E) values, ranging from 5 to 160 GPa, was measured for
494 all four samples. A total of 2420 indents were combined to create a frequency density plot, as
495 illustrated in Fig. 15. The bin size for each interval was set to 1 GPa. Additionally, a statistical
496 deconvolution technique [47, 48, 80] was employed to separate the mechanical response (mean
497 value, standard deviation, and volume fraction, f) into four phases: C-S-H gel, CH, WGP, and
498 residual clinker. The summarized results are shown in Tab. 9, and typical load-displacement curves
499 for these phases are presented in Fig. 14.

500 The results revealed nearly identical Young's modulus values of approximately 25 GPa for the
501 C-S-H gel phase in all three samples containing WGP (G20_REF, G20_0, G20_H). However, these
502 values were smaller compared to the reference samples, where E was found to be 32.6 ± 3.8 GPa.
503 Among the samples containing glass particles, the oxygen plasma-treated sample (G20_O) showed
504 the best performance, with C-S-H gel values closest to the reference, indicating a potential en-
505 hancement in the ITZ due to the oxygen plasma treatment. This finding is in agreement with the
506 SEM EDS analysis, which revealed a more compact and refined ITZ structure, characterized by
507 a smoother Ca/Si gradient and lower value Ca/Si indicating improved microstructural properties.
508 The shift of the main peak in Fig. 15 is noticeable and can be attributed to the fact that almost
509 all measurements in the cement matrix were performed in the ITZ for samples containing glass
510 particles. The second phase, primarily composed of CH crystals, exhibited modulus values within
511 the range of 41–44 GPa for all samples, consistent with literature values where E is measured in
512 the range of 37–45 GPa, depending on crystal orientation [47, 48].

513 Since the values of clinker were not primary interest in this investigation, only a small volume

514 fraction was measured for glass particle samples. The values are also in three cases smaller than
515 found in literature $E = 110\text{--}150$ GPa [81]. That can be attributed to that also clinker particles with
516 smaller dimensions were measured which are pressed into surrounding cement matrix resulting in
517 lower E values.

Figure 14: Typical load-displacement curves measured by nanoindentation.

Figure 15: Frequency plot of Young's modulus measured by nanoindentation.

Table 9: Young's modulus and volume fraction calculated by statistical deconvolution.

Phase	REF		G20_REF		G20_O		G20_H	
	E [GPa]	f [%]	E [GPa]	f (%)	E [GPa]	f [%]	E [GPa]	f [%]
C-S-H gel	32.6±3.8	62.3	25.7±4.3	56.5	25.5±5.4	54.9	25.3±5.1	55.1
CH	44.3±3.0	18.1	41.7±5.5	16.8	43.2±5.2	10.7	44.4±4.8	11.8
WGP	–	–	75.7±9.1	25.2	77.3±8.9	30.7	71.6±7.5	29.5
Clinker	98.4±42.8	19.5	121.4±19.1	1.5	104.5±7.2	3.7	106.5±22.8	3.6

518 4.5. Discussion of plasma treatment effect on WGP and its interaction with cement

519 Depending on the employed gas atmosphere (oxygen vs. hydrogen) for low temperature plasma
520 treatment, different plasma-material interaction processes and surface chemistry modifications can
521 be distinguished (Fig. 16). In case of the oxygen-based plasma discharge the high-energy elec-
522 trons create the plasma-activated oxygen and negatively charged oxygen ions, and also break the
523 molecular oxygen into atomic oxygen species. These reactive oxygen species serve multiple func-
524 tions: removing carbon-based contamination on the WGP surface (via CO and CO₂ formation
525 - i.e. so called plasma ashing of carbon species), passivating unsaturated dangling bonds with
526 oxygen, promoting oxygen-based surface functionality and hydrophilic properties. Conversely, in
527 hydrogen atmosphere-based plasma, the interaction between gas and electrons produced excited
528 hydrogen molecules, atomic hydrogen and positively charged hydrogen ions. These hydrogen-
529 based reactive species interact with carbon on the WGP surface and lead to the various hydro-
530 carbon compounds formation that are either removed (gaseous compounds) or precipitated (solid
531 compounds) on WGP, resulting in hydrogen (or more precisely hydrocarbon) based surface func-
532 tionality, hydrogen/CH_x passivation of unsaturated bonds and localized hydrophobic properties.

533 XPS analysis (Tab. 7 and Fig. 4) demonstrates that oxygen plasma treatment partially or com-
534 pletely removes the carbon contamination from WGP surface. At the nanoscale, this plasma treat-
535 ment disrupted the carbon shell on the glass particles, exposing the underlying WGP surface and
536 opening the cracks, thereby enhancing WGP reactivity. Moreover, oxygen-contained termination
537 on glass particles will behave as hydrophilic (Fig. 16) that creates a nanoscopic water reservoir

Figure 16: Schematic model for water interaction with plasma treated WGP.

538 facilitating more effective alkali ion exchange and silica-calcium exchange processes. Both of
 539 these processes will result in stronger pozzolanic reactions and prolonged hydration of the cement
 540 matrix. The increased WGP surface reactivity promotes more efficient formation of C-S-H gel
 541 within the interfacial transition zone (ITZ), resulting in reduced porosity and improved compressive
 542 strength.

543 In contrast, the hydrogen plasma treatment resulted rather in carbon redistribution or hydro-
 544 carbon coating formation on the WGP surface, potentially passivating nano-cracks in the glass
 545 surface. Taking into account that hydrogen termination or CH_x films reveal a hydrophobic surface,
 546 the insufficient water content around WGP limit the hydration process. Such conditions reduces
 547 the silica-calcium exchange processes and delays of C-S-H gel formation, resulting in waker ITZ
 548 development, higher porosity and lower compressive strength of samples compared to the oxygen-
 549 treated samples. The untreated reference samples exhibited an intermediate behavior, lacking the
 550 enhanced reactivity and ITZ bonding observed in oxygen-treated WGP.

551 These findings corroborate with the previous work by Hlůžek et al., who demonstrated that
 552 oxygen plasma treatment significantly enhances ITZ bonding, particularly in the interaction be-
 553 tween cement and fibers, by increasing the surface reactivity of supplementary materials, thereby

554 improving mechanical performance [68]. Similarly, Shafiei and Hillemeier observed analogous
555 effects in the interaction between cement and aggregates, where plasma-treated aggregates resulted
556 in improved compressive strength [33]. Furthermore, studies by Matos and Sousa-Coutinho and
557 Zhao et al. have emphasized the critical role of ITZ optimization in achieving a denser microstruc-
558 ture, as improved bonding at this interface significantly impacts the composite's strength and dura-
559 bility [49, 52]. The enhanced ITZ observed in this study, characterized by a homogeneous mi-
560 crostructure and reduced porosity in the oxygen-treated samples, confirms that the oxygen plasma
561 treatment promotes a more cohesive and durable matrix.

562 **5. Conclusions**

563 This study investigated the potential of plasma surface treatments to enhance the reactivity and
564 performance of waste glass powder in cementitious composites. The experimental work focused on
565 assessing the mechanical properties, microstructure, and the effects of plasma treatments (oxygen
566 and hydrogen). The findings revealed that oxygen plasma treatment significantly improved the
567 mechanical and microstructural properties of the composites, while hydrogen plasma treatment
568 demonstrated limited benefits. The key results of this study are as follows:

- 569 • Analyses of waste glass powder (XRF, SEM, XPS) confirmed a high SiO₂ content, support-
570 ing pozzolanic reactions. Oxygen plasma treatment effectively removed surface contami-
571 nants and increased hydrophilicity, enhancing the material's reactivity.
- 572 • Optimization of cement replacement with waste glass powder demonstrated that 10–20 wt.%
573 substitution is suitable for maintaining mechanical properties. Higher replacements (above
574 30 wt.%) resulted in decreased compressive and flexural strengths, corresponding to the
575 lower initial reactivity of glass powder.
- 576 • Oxygen plasma treatment increased compressive strength by approximately 10% for 10 and
577 20 wt.% replacements, attributed to improved hydration, pozzolanic activity, and densifi-
578 cation of interfacial transition zones. Hydrogen plasma treatment showed no significant
579 improvement due to the hydrophobic nature of the treated surfaces.

- 580 • Oxygen plasma treatment reduced fine pore volume (less than $0.01 \mu\text{m}$) and created a more
581 compact microstructure, enhancing resistance to degradation. Hydrogen plasma treatment
582 resulted in higher pore volumes and a less homogeneous microstructure.
- 583 • Oxygen plasma treatment led to a slight increase in hydrated products and a reduction in un-
584 hydrated clinker content, contributing to improved mechanical properties. Hydrogen plasma
585 treatment did not exhibit a comparable effect.
- 586 • Samples with oxygen plasma-treated WGP showed improved C-S-H gel stiffness, while
587 hydrogen plasma treatment had a weaker effect on the ITZ. Untreated samples exhibited
588 lower microstructure compactness.

589 The results underscore the potential of oxygen plasma treatment as an innovative and sustain-
590 able method to optimize the use of recycled glass in concrete applications. This approach not only
591 improves the material's performance but also supports environmental sustainability by promot-
592 ing the recycling of waste materials. Future research should focus on the long-term durability of
593 plasma-treated glass powder in various environmental conditions and its compatibility with other
594 cementitious additives to expand its application in sustainable construction practices.

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